

README

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Citation:

Pham-Truffert M and Angst M (2025) Replication files for ‘Citizens ditching cars: How do assessments of SDG interactions predict a modal shift towards low-carbon urban transport choices?’ by Myriam Pham-Truffert, Mario Angst, Thomas Breu and Maria J. Santos (2025). <https://zenodo.org/records/14900322>

We document the proper use of the replication files of the following manuscript:

Pham-Truffert M, Angst M, Breu T and Santos MJ (2025) Citizens ditching cars: How do assessments of SDG interactions predict a modal shift towards low-carbon urban transport choices? Environmental Research Letters. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ade817>.

Specifically, we report the required environment for the computation, our rights to use the data, and the procedure to reproduce our analysis. Specifically, we provide the code to reproduce:

1. theoretical causal model underlying our Bayesian approach (Figure 2 in the article)
2. pre-processing of the data
3. main analysis and its plots (Figures 3, 4 and 5 in the article)
4. additional figures in supplementary material (prior and posterior predictive checks and posterior distributions)

The aim is to enable the replication of the analysis by humans and to be transparent and as clear as possible regarding how we conducted our study.

Requirements for reproducing the analysis in your local environment

For the computation, you will need to run the script using R, with several packages required.

- **Software:** It is required that you have R installed (R Core Team 2024), and an editor you feel comfortable with (e.g., R Studio). The latest versions we used were 2024.12.1 for R Studio and the “Pile of Leaves” version 4.4.2 (2024-10-31) for R. To use the R package Bayesian regression models using Stan `brms` (Bürkner 2021), a C++ compiler is required. See [here](#) for guidance.
- **R Packages:** The replication procedure relies on numerous R packages. To facilitate installing the packages, a `renv.lock` file is provided, which lets you install all the necessary packages by calling `renv::restore()`, using the R package `renv`.

Reproducing the analysis with Nix

Alternatively, we supply a `nix_project/default.nix` file (created using the R package `rix`, using the script `rix_setup.R` included in this repository), which uses `Nix` to reproduce (most of) the environment the analysis was carried out in, including R and all R packages used.

To replicate the analysis in this way, you therefore only need Nix. Nix can be obtained most easily using the [Determinate Nix Installer](#), or from the [official download site](#).

Instructions in the case of using Nix:

- 1) Open a terminal inside `nix_project`
- 2) Build the nix environment with:

```
nix-build
```

- 3) Open a nix shell with:

```
nix-shell --pure
```

- 4) Run the main analysis script with:

```
Rscript main.R
```

Use of data

The two csv sheets provided in the `/data` folder of this repository are necessary to run the script:

- **Survey data:** The raw survey contained IP addresses of respondents. We removed IP addresses to ensure full anonymity of the responses, otherwise the data exactly matches the raw survey data.
 - ☒ The authors certify they have legitimate access and permission to use the above survey data.
- **Information on the municipalities:** We do some data linking to use official information on the different represented communes, to obtain the variable *urban zone* for each response (i.e., “City center”, “Principal core”, “Secondary core”, and “Urban ring”). Specifically, we used the data “su-f-21.03.01.01-2020” on the Swiss agglomerations from the (Office fédéral de la statistique 2024). The original data is accessible under: <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/fr/home/statistiques/themes-transversaux/analyses-spatiales/niveaux-geographiques.assetdetail.30665940.html>
 - ☒ The authors certify they do not use the data on the municipalities for commercial purposes and do comply with the condition of use set by the Federal Statistical Office.

Code

The script `main.R` reproduces the analysis and figures from the paper and the appendix. The script has a step-by-step structure to facilitate reuse by humans. Basic knowledge of R is expected. `main.R` calls three specific R scripts stored at `scripts/`:

In `scripts/dag.R`, you will reproduce the Figure 2 in the paper, which describes our theoretical causal model. It is presented with the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) notation (Cunningham 2021) and was produced with [DAGitty](#).

In `scripts/data_cleaning.R`, we load the data and preprocess the data frame, saving the output as a file `mydata.csv` at `data/clean_data`.

With `scripts/models.R` we present the main analysis. The script will reproduce Figures 3, 4 and 5 from the article, capturing the results of our main analysis. It also reproduces, in the last part of the script, the production of the figures from the article’s Supplementary Information A3 referring to the Bayesian Analysis Reporting Guidelines (BARG) proposed by Kruschke (2021). Specifically, we detail the following points:

- 1.E (Prior predictive check),

- 3.A (Posterior predictive check),
- 3.B (Summarize posterior of variables),

References

- Bürkner, Paul-Christian. 2021. “Bayesian Item Response Modeling in R with brms and Stan.” *Journal of Statistical Software* 100 (5): 1–54. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v100.i05>.
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- Office fédéral de la statistique. 2024. “Espace à Caractère Urbain de La Suisse 2020.” <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/fr/home/statistiques/themes-transversaux/analyses-spatiales/niveaux-geographiques.assetdetail.30665940.html>.
- R Core Team. 2024. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>.